

Heart Failure in Type 2 Diabetic Individuals Compared to Non-Diabetic People: A Comparative Clinical Investigation in Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital Ahmedabad

Parjanya Shah¹, Parth Shah², Dhruveshkumar Shaileshbhai Patel³, Rahul Sarraf⁴, Mitul Suthar⁵, Aryan Momin⁶

^{1,2}MBBS Graduate- Smt NHL Municipal Medical College, Ahmedabad, India

³Junior Resident, Department of Biochemistry, GMERS Medical College and Hospital, Gotri

⁴MBBS Smt. NHL Municipal Medical College

⁵Junior Resident Doctor, Department of Anatomy, GMERS Medical College and Hospital Gotri

⁶3rd Year MBBS, Smt NHL Ahmedabad, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Parjanya Shah

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Abstract:

In individuals with the established disease, type 2 diabetes mellitus raises the risk of morbidity and death and is a risk factor for incident heart failure. A rising illness burden is predicted by secular trends in the prevalence of heart failure and diabetes mellitus, which emphasize the need for efficient treatment approaches. The purpose of the study is to examine the clinical features of individuals with and without diabetes mellitus in Heart failure.

Methods: The cross-sectional study was on 35-70 years old adults with and without in DM. Indicators of Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) risk factors, including gender, age, blood pressure, dyslipidaemia, smoking, alcohol consumption, fasting blood sugar, creatinine, blood urea, waist circumference, body mass index, family history, physical inactivity were collected in the study.

Results: The 1852 participants were included. Triglycerides, alcohol intake, and smoking were found to be the variables linked to diabetics. Our study's findings indicate that there was a substantial prevalence of cardiovascular risk factors in diabetes mellitus. In this area, it is advised to cut back on alcohol and tobacco use in addition to managing hypertension, hyperlipidemia, and obesity.

Keywords: Type 2 diabetes, Heart failure, cardiovascular diseases.

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Introduction

Over 592 million individuals worldwide are predicted to have type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) by 2035, a sharp rise from the 382 million people with the disease in 2013—a number that is probably underestimated. [1,2] Two In the United States alone, 30.2 million persons, or 12.2% of the total, were projected to have diabetes mellitus in 2015. Of them, 7.2 million (23.3%) were either unaware of their condition or chose not to report it. [3]

Type 1 diabetes mellitus and type 2 diabetes are diverse illnesses that can have wide variations in both clinical manifestation and course of the disease. Most cases of diabetes mellitus (TMJ) account for 90% to 95% of cases. [4]. Because of this, the review will concentrate on the effects of pharmaceutical therapies for type 2 diabetes on the development of heart failure (HF). Individuals with diabetes mellitus are more than twice as likely to suffer heart failure (HF) than those without the

disease. [5, 6] Even after controlling for additional risk variables such age, hypertension, hypercholesterolemia, and coronary artery disease, there is still a higher incidence of heart failure (HF) in people with diabetes. Therefore, when the term "diabetic cardiomyopathy" was first used more than 40 years ago, it was meant to refer to ventricular dysfunction in diabetic individuals who did not have hypertension or coronary artery disease. [7] Its application has expanded, meanwhile, to include the myocardium's heightened susceptibility to malfunction that is typical of those who have diabetes mellitus. A recent study found that 44% of patients hospitalized for heart failure had diabetes mellitus, despite the fact that 10% to 15% of the general population has the disease. [1]

Studies have indicated that individuals with diabetes mellitus have an independent higher risk of death and rehospitalization when compared to individuals without diabetes who have heart failure.

[8] Furthermore, observational data indicates a correlation between an elevated HbA1c level and a higher incidence of HF. [9]. Thus, it's crucial to investigate if better glycemic control leads to better heart failure outcomes.

Diabetes in Heart failure

Diabetes as potential HF risk factor: Other CV risk factors like obesity, dyslipidemia, and hypertension are also linked to altered glycemic status. These variables, which are initial risk factors for HF occurrence [10], have been emphasized in the revised definition of HF. T2DM may thereby hasten the onset of vascular alterations, autonomic dysfunction, extracellular matrix collagen deposition, and coronary and systemic atherosclerosis [11]. This association could potentially complicate the risk assessment process, as it is uncertain to what extent the unfavourable consequence is attributable to glycemic dysfunction or the increased risk load.

In addition to raising Cardio vascular (CV) risk, T2DM is linked to low-grade inflammation, elevated blood pressure, advanced glycation end products (AGEs), atherogenic lipid profile, and renal disease [12,13]. Systemic vascular damage is caused by pro-atherogenic signals such as P selectin, vascular growth factors, and transforming growth factor β , which are produced when endothelial function is disrupted and vascular inflammation and an unfavorable lipid profile coexist.

Changes in intracellular signaling and energy substrate modification cause both cellular and vascular changes that result in increased myocardial vulnerability, fibrosis, and collagen deposition. Of all T2DM patients, over 90% are overweight, 70% have dyslipidemia, and nearly 70% have high blood pressure. [14]

Prevalence of T2DM in HF population and related risk: The prevalence of T2DM in HF patients has progressively increased from 12 to 22% in individuals 70 years of age or older during the past 20 years. [15] The general population's higher frequency of T2DM, improved diagnostic care, population aging, and the spread of preventative initiatives in developed nations could all be contributing factors to the current trend.

There are other ways that type 2 diabetes can impact the structure and function of the heart, but the most significant one has to do with the insulin resistance of the muscle, liver, and pancreatic cells. In these systems, the absence of an insulin response results in decreased levels of incretin from the gastrointestinal tract, increased renal glucose absorption, faster lipolysis, systemic glucotoxicity, and fatty acid lipotoxicity. Notably, cardiac damage can result from a variety of changes, including

endothelial (higher RAA activity, vascular growth factors, decreased NO synthase), metabolic (lipogenesis and gluconeogenesis), renal (increasing Na and glucose resorption), myocardial (sarcomeric stiffness and fibrosis overexpression), and inflammatory disorders (increased expression of interleukines facilitating thrombogenesis).

The various HF patterns and heart structural adaptations may be explained by the prevalence of each pathological cause. Common antidiabetic medications cannot treat individuals with glycaemic related metabolic diseases, which are the cause of these metabolic and energetic dysfunctions. [16,17]

Aim & Objectives

Aim: The aim of the study and compare the clinical characteristics among Diabetic mellites patients with and without HF and non- Diabetic mellites with and without Heart failure.

Objectives: To investigate cause-specific outcomes and trends associated with type 2 diabetes among individuals with incident HF.

Methods

Study methodology

Study Design: Cross sectional study

Study Site: This study was conducted at PSM Hospital & associated tertiary care hospital in Gandhinagar, Gujarat and patients will be recruited from medicine and diabetic OPDs.

Sample Size Calculation: Heart failure and anatomical anomalies in the heart, along with related cardiovascular risk, are all part of HF. The ACC/AHA/HFSA (Heart Failure Society of America) HF guidelines and the Universal Definition and Classification of Heart Failure task force have both recently validated useful methods for classifying the various stages of HF.

Clinical and biochemical information would be collected from the medical records based on sociodemographic criteria. will be divided into four groups.

1. DM with Heart failure
2. DM without Heart failure
3. Non-DM with Heart failure
4. Non-DM without Heart Failure

Demographic and clinical characteristics: The age groups' substantial differences in BMI, eGFR, and age. Older than persons in other age groups are those who have DM and HF. Between the groups, there is a notable variation in the prevalence of CAD, dyslipidemia, and hypertension.

Results and Discussion

In this study, there were 1852 DM patients; 1132 (61.1%) were female and 720 (38.2%) were male. The average age of the participants was 55.92 ± 8.17 years. Furthermore, the average age of the individuals in the group with diabetes was considerably greater than that of the group without the condition (56.31 ± 7.98 years against 54.37 ± 8.74 years, P value < 0.001). It is evident that there were notable differences between the two groups in terms of education level, marital status, smoking, alcohol consumption, history of hypertension, history of ischemic heart disease, family history of stroke. (P value < 0.05). The prevalence of risk factors in the group without diabetic included 32.9% abdominal obesity (95% confidence interval: 29.18–38.62), 17.7% obesity (95% confidence interval: 17.72–21.68), 27.1% hypertriglyceridemia (95% confidence interval: 22.67–31.53), 15.8% hypertension (95% confidence interval: 12.17–19.43), 16.8% smoking

(95% confidence interval: 12.17–19.43), 12.7% history of ischemic heart disease (95% confidence interval: 9.39–16.01), 4.9% alcohol consumption (95% confidence interval: 3.55–8.25), and low HDL 1.3% (95% confidence interval: 0.18–2.42), respectively.

The risk factors in the group was reported as 85.5% hypertriglyceridemia (95% confidence interval: 78.54–82.46), 75.9% abdominal obesity (95% confidence interval: 73.76–78.04), 64% hypertension (95% confidence interval: 61.66–66.39), 48% low HDL (95% confidence interval: 45.51–50.49), 43.8% obesity (95% confidence interval: 41.33–46.27), 25.3% smoking (95% confidence interval: 20.22–24.38), 16% history of ischemic heart disease (95% confidence interval: 18.80–19.20), and 9.4% alcohol consumption (95% confidence interval: 7.95–10.85), respectively. Table 1 shows that the for mentioned factors was statistically significant in both groups (P value < 0.05).

Table 1(A): A comparison of demographic and clinical characteristics in type 2 diabetes mellitus non-diabetic & diabetic patients. Medium (first quarter-third quarter) for age and frequency (%) is reported for qualitative variables

Variables	Total (n = 1933)	Without Diabetics (n = 387)	With diabetics (n = 1546)	P value	
Age	57 (50–62)	55/5 (47–61)	57 (51–63)	0.001	
Gender (%)	Male	720 (37/2%)	211 (54%)	501 (33/1%)	0.001
	Female	1132 (62/8%)	198 (46%)	934 (66/9%)	
Family history of ischemic heart disease (%)	Yes	226 (14/3%)	63 (16/3%)	163 (13/8%)	0/208
	No	1457 (85/7%)	324 (83/7%)	1133 (86/2%)	
Family history of heart attack (%)	Yes	203 (11/5%)	45 (11/6%)	158 (11/5%)	0/950
	No	1610 (88/5%)	342 (88/4%)	1268 (88/5%)	
Family history of high blood pressure (%)	Yes	340 (19/7%)	82 (21/2%)	258 (19/3%)	0/397
	No	1253 (80/3%)	305 (78/8%)	930 (80/7%)	
Family history of diabetes mellitus (%)	Yes	446 (22/0%)	95 (24/5%)	415 (21/4%)	0/183
	No	1007 (78/0%)	292 (75/5%)	715 (78/6%)	
Family history of stroke (%)	Yes	125 (8/3%)	43 (11/1%)	82 (7/6%)	0/027
	No	1672 (91/7%)	344 (88/9%)	1328 (92/4%)	0.001

The individuals with diabetes had significantly higher median BMI, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, heart rate, triglyceride, ALP, and TG to HDL ratios, and significantly lower HDL than the non-diabetic group.

Table 1(B):

Variables	Total (n = 1933)	Without diabetic (n = 387)	With diabetic (n = 1546)	P value
BMI	28/66 (25/84–31/93)	26/45 (24/12–29/01)	29/30 (26/40–32/49)	0.001
Systolic blood pressure	115 (100–125)	108 (100–118/5)	115 (100–125)	0.001
Diastolic blood pressure	70 (65–80)	70(65–80)	75 (65–80)	0.001
Heart rate	76 (70–82)	74 (68–80)	76 (70–83)	0.001
Fasting blood sugar	144 (114–188)	143 (111–182/25)	145 (115–189)	0/3
Triglyceride	165 (121–229)	126 (100–160)	179 (132/5–240)	0.001
Cholesterol	193 (167–223)	191/5 (164–218)	194 (167–225)	0/098
HDL	56 (49–64)	59 (52–66)	56 (48–63)	0.001
LDL	100 (78–124)	99 (80–125)	100 (78–124)	0/430
Creatinine	1 (0/9–1/2)	1 (0/9–1/2)	1 (0/9–1/2)	0/143
TG to HDL ratio	2/96 (2/07–4/29)	2/15 (1/60–2/84)	3/22 (2/25–4/49)	0.001

Table 2: A comparison of the median anthropometric and laboratory indices of type 2 diabetes mellitus patients with and without diabetic.

Variables		OR (95% CI)	P value
TG to HDL ratio		1/42 (1/30–1/55)	0.001
Abdominal obesity	No	ref	–
	Yes	13/69 (9/77–19/29)	0.001
Smoking	No	ref	–
	Yes	5/52 (3/67–8/55)	0.001
Alcohol consumption	No	Ref	–
	Yes	4/089 (2/32–7/23)	0.001
Hypertension	No	Ref	–
	Yes	13/52 (9/55–19/19)	0.001

Thus, there was an increase in the risk of diabetes by 5.60% (95% confidence interval: 3.67–8.55) associated with smoking, 4.1% (95% confidence interval: 2.32–7.23) associated with alcohol consumption, 1.42% (95% confidence interval: 1.30–1.55) associated with TG to HDL ratio, 13.73% (95% confidence interval: 9.77–19.29) associated with abdominal obesity, and 13.54% (95% confidence interval: 9.55–19.19) associated with hypertension. It is linked to a higher risk of getting diabetes since two of the five causes of the disease are abdominal obesity and hypertension.

In the present investigation, DM patients' TG to HDL ratio, smoking habit, and alcohol intake were also found to be risk factors for DM. Mottillo et al. and Lindsay et al. [18,19] verified these findings. Slagter et al. claim that there is a dose-dependent relationship between alcohol and cigarette usage and the risk of diabetes and some of its components. [20] It has been discovered that the three main risk factors for cardiovascular disease in diabetic patients are smoking, high blood pressure, and high levels of LDL.

Other risk factors for cardiovascular problems include inflammation, low HDL cholesterol, insulin resistance, and hyperglycemia. [21] Elevated fasting glucose levels are highly correlated with cardiovascular events in this cohort, according to research by Sadabadi F et al. [22] The sociodemographic or lifestyle characteristics that were previously stated may also be responsible for the disparities seen in this study.

According to earlier studies, the main underlying cause of diabetes is obesity, especially central obesity, which leads to a hereditary predisposition to other risk factors such as dyslipidaemia and hypertension [23]. The current study found that the prevalence of abdominal obesity in DM patients with diabetes was 75.9%, whereas it was 33.9% in diabetic patients without diabetes.

This study's findings are higher than Cheng et al.'s, which found that 91.6% of DM [24] patients had abdominal obesity. In addition to raising the risk of dyslipidaemia and coronary artery disease [25], central obesity is a significant risk factor for

diabetics and DM [26]. In this investigation, the prevalence of hypertension was found to be 15.8% in the group without MtS and 64% in the group with MtS. Previous research has demonstrated the connection between high blood pressure and metabolic syndrome. [27] In hypertension patients, metabolic syndrome is more common than in the general population, and among newly diagnosed hypertensive patients, the prevalence of diabetes is rising, with elevated blood pressure serving as a signal for diabetes. [28] This study also demonstrated that diabetes has a higher prevalence of hypertension in DM patients. As a result, controlling high blood pressure and other CVD risk factors has changed. [29,30]

Conclusions

The findings of this study imply that patients with type 2 diabetes and heart failure may be benefiting from preventative methods to type 2 diabetes care in terms of decreased extra cardiovascular risk. However, type 2 diabetes in those without heart failure is a significant and ongoing public health issue. The unique cause-specific outcome trends that we found in this high-risk group support the application of early cardiovascular risk prevention strategies for other high-risk groups. They also point to the urgent need for patient-centred multimorbidity care and earlier comorbidity management in type 2 diabetes in order to lessen the disease's mounting burden.

Limitation of the study

To assess CAD, not every patient was undergoing a coronary angiography; instead, the diagnosis is made based on the patient's medical history, ECG, and echocardiogram results.

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